

LEARNING THE INFLUENCE OF PROXIMAL FIBULAR OSTEOTOMY TO BIOMECHANICS OF JOINT AT VARUSAL DEFORMITY OF KNEE JOINT OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Objective. Among large support joints, the rate of injury due to degenerative-dystrophic changes of the knee joint remains high, leading to a sharp disruption of the normal movement biomechanics of the human musculoskeletal system, patients needing additional support and a significant decrease in functional and social adaptation [1].

.An analysis of recent literature shows that the initial change in knee joint biomechanics occurs in 20% of people, of which 87% of patients with deformable osteoarthritis have varus deformity, and 100% of patients over 51 years of age have knee joint biomechanical disorders [2].

According to scientists, after the operation of proximal fibular osteotomy (PFO) in deformed osteoarthritis of the knee, due to the weakening of the external components of the knee joint changes the balance of the joint and the mechanism of redistribution of load on the outer and inner plateaus.

Materials and methods. Into investigation included 152 patients with acute pain syndrome varusal deformed arthritis of knee aged from 40 till 60 yy, treated in the department of sport trauma of Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of traumatology and orthopedy and in the department of emergency traumatology of Bukhara branch of Republican Research Center of the Emergency Medicine at the period from 2018 to 2021 yy. All patients made application of knee joint debridement and PFO by standard technique. Achieved results were analyzed by indicators of KSS (Knee Society Score).

Results. The KSS scale was used to assess knee joint function, and the results were evaluated on days 1, 2, 3 before surgery and 1 and 6 months after surgery. In the assessment by the KSS method, the knee joint was assessed based

on its clinical-functional status and the stability of the tibio-lateral joint, scores were summarized in the evaluation of results: <60 points - unsatisfactory; 60–69 points - satisfactory; 70–79 points - good; 80–100 points - rated very good. The results of surgical procedures performed in 133 patients of control groups and 19 patients of the basic groups with osteoarthritis of the knee joint were evaluated based on the analysis of clinical and functional indicators of the KSS scale.

The improvement in knee joint function was also explained by a decrease in the criterion of "bending and unbending contracture" of the knee joint, i.e. the developed knee joint "bending contracture - 16 - 20 and > 20 degree" in the control group decreased by 14% and 1.4%, "unbending contracture" decreased by 7.5%, and in the basic group of patients "bending contracture" decreased by 15%, after surgery "> 20 degrees. Patients with "bending contracture of the knee joint" were not identified. Patients with "> 20 degree knee unbending contracture" decreased by 10% and "> 20 degree knee unbending contracture" contract were not identified.

Conclusion, an analysis of the results obtained in the basic and control group patients showed that the complex application of knee joint derivative and PFO surgeries significantly improved the percentage of positive outcomes.

